

Scanning Electron Microscopy studies of phoretic mite *Parasitus heliocopridis* Oudemans, 1910 associated with *Heliocopris midas* & *Onitis philemon*

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Abstract:

Parasitus heliocopridis Oudemans, 1910 were reported associated with *Heliocopris midas* & *Onitis philemon* (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae). The first report of this phoretic mite species was revealed from Maharashtra, India, and is accompanied by scanning electron micrographs and its morphometry.

Keywords: Species, Revealed, Morphometry, Report.

Introduction:

Mites are small unsegmented, microscopic animals placed in the phylum Arthropoda and class Arachnida. They have extensive symbiotic activities and interrelationships with insects. These associates could be ectoparasitic, endoparasitic predacious (feeding on hemolymph of the host), phoretic (Passive transport), exudates feeders, and fungivorous (Metwally *et al.* 2014, Sarangi 2014). Farish & Axtell (1971) defined phoresy in which "one organism attaches to the outer body surface of another organism for a short period during which the attached organism (termed the phoretic or phoront) stops both their development and feeding, such activity resulting in transfer from unsuited areas for further development of the individuals. Quickly changing biotic environments or density-dependent factors may set up an unfavorable habitat for these mites because of this these mites use coexisting arthropods to move to new favorable habitats (Bajerlein *et al.* 2013).

The mites have evolved different attachment organs adapted to use other animals to

move from one habitat to another, known as phoresy (Binns, 1982). Some species of mites attach themselves to other animals using permanent organs such as modified chelicerae (females of Macrochelidae), claws and pulvilli of legs (deutonymphs of Parasitidae), or ventral suckers (hypopodesin, e.g., Histiostomatidae, Carpoglyphidae, Acaridae) and claspers (hypopodes in Glycyphagidae) and anal pedicel in deutonymphs of Uropodina mites (Bajerlein *et al.* 2013).

The substance which is needed to make the anal pedicel in deutonymphs of uropodid mites is secreted by a gland that is located dorsally over the colon, initially that secreted substance is in a liquid state but hardens when it comes in contact with air (Bajerlein and Witalinski 2012). This pedicel serves as a connection between the mite and its carrier host, the one end of the anal pedicel connected to the anal region of the deutonymph and the other end connected to the body surface of the carrier host. Afterward, reaching an appropriate habitat deutonymph leaves the carrier for further growth,

but the pedicel generally remains connected to the carrier's body (Bajerlein *et al.* 2016).

Materials And Methods:

Mite associates of invertebrates were recovered by collecting and examining the insect host. Insects were collected during the night using insect nets, night traps, forceps, and directly by hand in the light source. Insects were brought to the laboratory and immediately examined the body's different parts such as head, thorax, legs, elytra, regions between thorax and abdomen under a Stereo binocular dissecting microscope. Mites from the insect body were separated using a fine camel brush moistened in 4 % lactic acid and brushed the insect's entire body in a clean Petri dish. For scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image analysis, mites were cleaned and cleared in washing for 15 min in 0.05 % HCL (Hydrochloric acid) or sometimes 4% lactic acid. They were then dehydrated by washing for 10 min in a graded series of ethanol alcohols (40 %, 50 %, 60 %, 70 %, 80 %, and 90 %) and finally by 3 x 15 min washes in absolute alcohol. Then the mites were then critical point dried. This protocol was taken from Hart & Fain (1988) and Montasser (2013). Measurements of specimens were taken using a Leica trinocular research microscope with an attached camera and sometimes Image J software was also used.

Result and discussion:

The first report of this phoretic mite species was revealed from Maharashtra, India, and is accompanied by scanning electron micrographs and its morphometry.

Systematic Account

Family : **Parasitidae Oudemans, 1901**

Genus : ***Parasitus* Latreille, 1795**

***Parasitus heliocopridis* Oudemans, 1910**

Habitat/Host: *Heliocopris midas*, *Onitis philemon*

Locality of collection: Hadapsar, Dist. Pune & Shevgaon Dist. Ahmednagar, Maharashtra, India

Female:

Measurements:

The deutonymphs varies in size, depending on the stage of life cycle. Collected female deutonymph ranges from 1486-1929 μm in length and 1008-1458 μm in width.

Gnathosoma:

Gnathosoma measures 550-582 μm in length and 244-279 μm in width. pedipalps measures 425-440 μm in length.

Body:

Idiosoma of this species is oval. Colour of this species varies from yellow to whitish brown.

Dorsal site:

Dorsal idiosoma consist of two well separated shields, anteriorly podonotal shield (600-647 μm in length and 588-650 μm in width) with 20 pairs of setae and opisthonotal shield (324-379 μm in length and 399-422 μm in width) with 13 pairs of setae posteriorly with Z3 longest (390-420 μm in length). These dorsal setae well differ in the length and some end with pilose.

Ventral site:

sternal plate 390-420 μm in length and 152-183 μm (at the level of st2) in width; with four pairs of setae (st1-4).

Male:

Measurements:

Male deutonymph ranges from 1099-1500 μm in length and 763-1022 μm in width.

Gnathosoma: Gnathosoma measures 400-426 μm in length and 220-244 μm in width. pedipalps measures 425-440 μm in length.

Dorsal site: Dorsal idiosoma consist of two well separated shields, anteriorly podonotal shield (557-600 μm in length and 498-672 μm in width) with 20 pairs of setae and opisthonotal shield (300-406 μm in length and 380-505 μm in width) with 13 pairs of setae posteriorly with Z3 longest

(409-446 μm in length). These dorsal setae well differ in the length and some end with pilose.

Legs: I-leg 1599-1731 μm , II-leg 1127-1277 μm , III-leg 1223-1277 μm , IV-leg 1540-1635 μm . The legs attached to ventrally on idiosoma and divided into six segments. Leg IV is longer than I, II and III leg.

Distribution:

Malkarova, 1996 given a distribution of *P. heliocopridis* from India (Region unspecified), Ceylon, Malaysia, Indonesia.

Remark: This species differs from *P. copridis* and *P. lunariphilus* by dorsal chaetotaxy, j5 and j6 long, s5 & s6 almost equal in length.

Table. 4 Measurements (μm) of *Parasitus heliocopridis*

Specimens	Body size of male deutonymph		Body size of female deutonymph	
	Length	Width	Length	Width
1	1500	1022	1486	1008
2	1297	802	1929	1458
3	1099	763	1819	1249
4	1383	907	1655	1060
5	1455	998	1518	1048
Range	1099-1500	763-1022	1486-1929	1008-1458

PLATE 1

Fig.1. *Parasitus heliocopridis* Female sternal plate

Fig.2. *Parasitus heliocopridis* Female Gnathosoma

Fig.3. *Parasitus heliocopridis* female, Podonotal and opisthonotal shields with distinct setae pattern

Fig.4. *Parasitus heliocopridis* Female Anal plate

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